

The Historical Significance of the Tribal Religious Cults of Tripura: An Overview

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This paper discusses in details about the various tribal religious cults of Tripura. Nineteen tribal communities reside in Tripura, who belong to diverse ethnic, linguistic and religious groups. This paper explains the main characteristics of the tribal religious cults of Tripura. The most important universal feature of tribal faith in Tripura is that it ranges from the vaguest and supernatural worship to the deepest anthropomorphism. It is a universal fact that the rites and rituals of the tribal people vary from those of the stately temples of Agartala to those of the Tipras, the Reangs, the Noatias, the Jamatias, the Uchois, the Kalais, the Rupinis who worship their fourteen Gods and Goddesses with conventional tribal rules, beliefs and practices. But it is of utmost significance that all the forms of tribal worship have similarities with the Brahmanic cults. It is a curious mixture of Hinduism and animism, the old gods have not yet been replaced and they are worshipped side by side with those of the Hindus by tribal priests. They worship the elements such as the God of water, the God of fire, the God of forests, the God of earth etc. The various tribal religious cults of Tripura, such as Kharchi Puja, Ker Puja, Garia Puja, Ganga Puja, Lampra Puja, Mailooma and Kholooma Puja, Tuima and Sangram Puja etc; we find lots of similarities from Hinduism. It is in this background that this paper discusses in details some of the tribal cultural practices of Tripura. The paper comprises of three parts. The first part briefly touches the conceptual issues and review of literature; the second elaborates upon the practices and the third is in the form of conclusion.

Besides literary information from published and unpublished sources, my field studies to different tribal areas and observation of the cultural practices have been useful in the preparation of this paper.

I

As per *Cambridge Learner's Dictionary*, the meaning of cult is "A religious group whose ideas are considered strange by many people." It also means "someone or something that has become very popular with a particular group of people." Now the question arises, "what is religion?" According to Raghuvir Singha, It is believed that religion is

community understood as a belief that mankind has in some invisible controlling power with a related emotion and sense of morality.¹ Emile Durkheim defined religion as “a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to say things set apart and forbidden—beliefs and practices which unite into one single moral community called a church, all those who adhere to them. *Oxford Dictionary* describes religion as “the belief in and/or worship of a superman controlling power, specially a personal God or Gods.” It is absolutely true that many scholars have researched the tribal religious cults of Tripura. However, some of the earlier writings are too specialised to understand for general readers and researchers. They are much specialised researches on the development of pre-colonial periods or even the colonial and post colonial period with a particular tribe or tribal faith, belief and practices. Further, large number of researches has been conducted on the origin, development and contribution of Christianity in Tripura. In my previous researches on Tripura, I have reviewed good number of them; hence, to avoid the repetition, I am writing some of them only here.² Besides these problematic areas in a number of earlier researches, in a recent publication on the religion of northeast India, Tripura has not found a place. However, in the same book the article of Amrendra Kumar Thakur provides a comprehensive study of Buddhism in Arunachal Pradesh. In his article Thakur has explained the process of assimilation between the pre-Buddhist and Buddhist elements of society excellently, while describing the aspects of Buddhism objectively.³

Tribal life in India, written by N.K Bose explains in detail about the overall tribal life of India, but it does not talk much about the tribal religious cults of Tripura. The word Animism and Animatism etc. have been discussed nicely in my present research paper.⁴ Raghuvir Sinha has also explained in a detailed manner about the overall religion and culture of North-eastern India in his book *Religion and Culture of North Eastern India*. But this book does not explain broadly on the tribal religious cults of Tripura.⁵ This is why, I have tried to fill up the gap in my research paper. The book *Tripura* authored by S.N. Guha Thakurta does not talk much upon the lives and religious cults of the tribal people of Tripura.⁶ This is why based on my practical observation I have tried to elaborate on the religious cults of tribal people of Tripura. Nalini Ranjan Roychoudhury, has written his famous book *Tripura Through the Ages* which has scanty information about the religious cults of the tribal people of Tripura.⁷ The book *Indian Society* written by S.C. Dube is one of the best secondary sources to trace out social lives of tribal people of India, but is unable to make quite worthy mention regarding

the religious tribal life of Tripura.⁸ The Book *A Cultural History of Tripura*, written by Jagadish Gan Chaudhuri does not explain the tribal religious cults of Tripura in detail. Therefore, I have tried to explain in detail about tribal religious cults to fill up the gap in the historiography of religious life of Tripura.⁹

II

If we glance over the religious beliefs and rites, temples and pilgrimage in Tripura we can easily ponder over the impact of geographical influences of rivers, forests and high hills, which are always held in high esteem. In Tripura, rivers, forests and mountains are deified and worshipped by the local people. The source of river or a confluence of rivers is believed to be very sacred place Dumbur in Tripura is one of the best pilgrimage places, where thousands of people assemble on the day of Poush Sankranti in January every year. If we brood over the tribal religious cults of Tripura, we find that it is full of varied forms of nature and indigenous Gods and Goddesses, a mixed way of Hindu way of life and of the religious practices and beliefs of local indigenous Gods and Goddesses too. Historically, their forefathers worshipped nature and natural forms of Gods and Goddesses. But after a long span of time due to better livelihood, education and material influences of modernity, some of the tribal communities changed their religion and became Christians.

If we look into the historical perspective of the tribal religious cults in Tripura, we find that the most significant universal feature of tribal faith in Tripura is that it ranges from the vaguest animism and supernatural worship to the deepest anthropomorphism. It is a fact that the rites and rituals of the tribal people vary from those of the stately temples of Agartala to those of the Tipras, the Reangs, the Noatias, the Jamatias, the Uchois, the Kalais and the Rupinis, who worship their indigenous fourteen Gods and Goddesses with conventional tribal rites and beliefs and practices. But it should be remembered that the form of worship springs from true love, therefore, we find no differences in the field of tribal religion from the Brahmanical faith.¹⁰

Sects and cults add to the complexity of Hinduism. Cults involve esoteric beliefs and practices and are often confined to particular individuals or their families and do not extend to an entire caste; their community is a small and secret. Aghorpanth, Kashmir Shaivism and several Tantrik schools can be cited as examples of cults. They are tolerated, if not encouraged by Hinduism.¹¹ Religion is a transforming experience. It is not a theory of God, but it is a spiritual consciousness.

Beliefs and conduct, rites and ceremonies, dogmas and authorities are subordinate to the art of self discovery and contact with the Divine. The most general terms in which culture could be explained would be something like this "The sense of ultimate values which a certain society has and according to which it wants to shape its life."¹²

Practically the Tripuri religion is based on Hinduism. The habitants of the interior though perform their traditional ritual according to their custom; many of their God and Goddesses are akin to the Hindu Gods and Goddesses particularly in the nature of belief. Only the mode of worship is completely different. Besides, the neighbouring Hindu Bengalis have a distinct shape of their deities, which is absolutely found absent among the Tripuris. In the Tripuri community bamboo made structure represents the form of the deities.¹³ Tripura is the state which is narrated as the land of the temples of Gods and Goddesses. The rulers of Tripura were devotees of Hindu religion and culture. They were patron of Saiva and Sakti-cult and in the later period they became devotees of Vaishnava cult.¹⁴ According to N.K. Bose "One might indeed say that tribals can be regarded as being fully absorbed in the Hindu fold if Brahmin priest perform Brahmanical ceremonies for them during the three critical events of birth, marriage and death. If the latter are still celebrated by tribal rituals, then the communities are still true to their own faith in spite of the fact that in the outer fringes of their culture, they participate in some of the ceremonies of their neighbours."¹⁵ If we observe the religious tribal practices of Tripura, we find the tribal communities have two types of priests for example- (i) Brahmin Priests and the (ii) Ochai people.

It is significant that the Tipras along with the Noatias, the Uchois, the Reangs, the Jamatias and the Kalais and others have two kinds of priests. At present, it is found that they engage Brahmin priests during the three main events of birth, marriage and death. Thus, we find the Hindu identity of the Tipras along with the other tribal communities in Tripura. The remarkable point is that the tribal people living in accessible regions of forests, hills and hill slopes have their own Ochais (tribal priests) only and the pujas as well as all religious ceremonies are performed by them following the traditional beliefs and practices.¹⁶ It is of the utmost significance that the tribal people participate in some of the ceremonies of their Hindu neighbours. In Tripura it is observed that all the tribal communities are described as 'animist.' According to the views of A.E. Porter in his census report of 1931 pointed out to show that the term 'animist' previously used to describe the religion

of tribal people may be replaced by the vaguer, but more satisfactory term 'tribal religion'.¹⁷

Some of the tribal cults can be described in the following manner—

Animism

As per The Concise Oxford dictionary of Archaeology "Animism is a belief that events in the world are mobilized by the activities of spirits." It is observed that the Halams extremely believe in the existence and activities of soul in man, animals and plants. The most of the Hindu Halams believe that high mountains, hills, trees and bamboos are the abodes of the spirits or Godlings. The same type of belief is generally found among the Tipras, Noatias, Jamatias, Reangs, Kuki and Uchois. As per the views of Sri Debapriya Deb Barman, "Tripuris call the soul of human body as 'FALA.' They believe that when a man falls asleep, the soul goes and returns from the body temporarily and returns into the body." The belief in spirit is an important aspect of the religious life of Tipras. Even more, some of the hills and big trees are indicative to them as the dwelling of the evil spirits.¹⁸ In case of the Jamatias, Animism is a unique factor. They worship the supernatural spirits and forces; although they succumb to Hinduism, but the essence of animism is one of the characteristic features of their religions like Tipras, Reangs and others. The spirits of God or Godling or deities is indicated by the word 'Matai' and accordingly to the Anthropological point of view all their primitive deities are nothing, but the Nature deities and spirits only. Animism also prevails among the Uchois and they adore the evil forces of Nature. The Mundas prefer to call themselves Hindu while they retain the cult of their tribal deities, Animism plays an important part in their religious life.¹⁹

Animatism

Truly speaking the meaning of Animatism is "The belief that inanimate objects have consciousness." If we observe the lifestyles of all the 19 tribes of Tripura, we find that the belief of animatism is found among the Tipras, Noatias, Reangs, Jamatias, Kukis, Halams, Uchois, Oraons, Santhals and others. The Reangs believe the natural objects from the stone to the mountain are said to have life in themselves. The Kukis generally, believe that the mountain 'Longtharai' is a deity and they worship it. Through the centuries, the Tipra community observe the 'Randhak' Puja as a part of the Garia Puja. The 'Randhak' is a symbolic representation of the spirit who is responsible for the welfare

of the house. Among the Uchois, Noatias and Jamatias, the 'Randhak' Puja is a marked feature and used as the symbols of animatism.

Shamanism

It is a system of religious practice. History is the evidence of this fact that the word 'Shamanism' is often associated with Indigenous and tribal societies, and involves beliefs that shamans with a connection to the other world, have the power to heal the sick, communicate with spirits and escort souls of the dead to the afterlife. Though Modern society is blessed with 21st century innovations, still Shamanism also plays a pivotal role as far as the tribal religious cults are concerned. In the tribal societies of Tripura the Ochais (or the Priests) have the significant roles to play during the time of sacred occasions. The Ochai is the priest of the tribal communities. He is known to have all the details of good and bad spirits. It is observed that the Ochais are such kind of sacred specialists of the tribal community, who find out the cause of disease and through their spells and pujas or sacrifices they drive away the spirits. Sometimes, they also treat the ailing persons by providing herbs to them. The influence of Shamanism over the people of Tripura seems to be very great. The Tipras are completely under the influence of the Priest Ochai, who has a pivotal role in the society. Apart from the pujas and religious rites, the Ochai is also a medicine man. Shamanism is the main religious belief of the Kukis, Noatias and Oraons. Even the Jamatias also have full faith and belief in Shamanism.

Fertility Cult

Fertility cult plays a very significant role in the tribal religious cults of Tripura. It is noteworthy that the tribal communities of Tripura perform some rites to promote fertility of crops, domestic animals and woman beings. Some of the female deities are as follows:-

Tooima— She is the Goddess of water. This diety is worshipped as a household Goddess as well as a village Goddess as a precautionary measure against the attack of Pox, Cholera etc. The tribal people worship the Tooima deity on the river. As the water helps to spread the diseases; so they worship the Goddess of the river, not to contain the disease. To worship the deity one he-goat or buffalo is needed as offering.²⁰

Mailooma— This female deity is worshipped by the tribal communities in a better manner, because 'Mailooma' is the Goddess of Paddy and other crops. For livelihood purpose, the worship of 'Mailooma' is very much needed.

Khooloma— She is the Goddess of cotton. As a matter of fact, Mailooma and Khooloma are worshipped jointly for wealth and prosperity.

Haichukma— She is the Goddess, who rules over animals and forests. The Tripuri believe that when any domesticated animal is lost, they pray to this deity to get back the animal and promise a worship to this deity.

Besides female deities, some male deities are also worshipped so that the prosperity and well-being of the tribal community can be obtained. Such male deities are as follows:

- (a) Sangram— who is the God of wealth and prosperity
- (b) Burasa— He is a male deity, who stands for diseases.
- (c) Sakalakmatai— He is a male deity of wealth.
- (d) Kalia and Garia— These two male deities are Gods of successes, who are worshipped individually or collectively.

Sakta Cult, Saivism and Vaishnavism— Truly speaking these cults of Hindu religion have lots of impact on the religious lives of the tribal communities. The Halams and the Noatias are generally the followers of the 'Sakta Cult' but most of the people belonging to the Kalai and Rupini sections of the former tribe follow Vaishnavism. The form of worship practiced by the above mentioned tribes is akin to that of the other Hindus. Even the tribal people of Tripura worship Lord Shiva, in the form of their tribal God named as 'Matai-Katar'. The word 'Matai' means God and 'Katar' means Great or Supreme. In this manner, the supreme deity of Tripura is identified with Siva Mahadeva.²¹ There are lots of temples of Lord Shiva in Tripura, which is worshipped by all the tribal communities of Tripura. This is the best example of the prevalence of 'Saivism' in the tribal religious cults of Tripura. Many temples of Goddess Kali has been constructed by the rulers of Tripura. One of the well known and prominent temples is 'Tripura Sundari' temple, where lots of tribal people worship the Goddess of power. In this manner 'Sakti Cult' is prevalent among the tribal religious cults of Tripura.

III

On the basis of above discussion, by way of conclusion, it can be summed up that the religious outlook of the indigenous people of Tripura is centred round the ceremonies and worship of the Gods, Goddesses and spirits. They maintain a distinguished code of rites and rituals, beliefs and superstitions. Further, the tribal cults of Tripura are based on their rich tradition. Simultaneously, their religious beliefs and practices are deeply influenced by the Hindu Mythology. Besides male Gods, they also worship female deities for their welfare and prosperity. The

prevalence of Saivism can also be observed in the tribal religious cults of Tripura, which are the resemblance of the impact of Hindu religion over the traditional indigenous religious lives of the tribes of Tripura. Finally, we can say that the tribal people of Tripura are animistic and at the same time they believe in the existence of God in all elements of Nature. Thus, it is observed that God is one and is Omnipresent and the religious life presents an assimilation of religious beliefs of the Hindu mythology and the tribal traditional beliefs.

Notes and References

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- 16 Priyabarta Bhattacharjee, *Tribal Pujas and Festivals in Tripura*, *op.cit.*, pp.8-9.
- 17 Extract from *1931 Census Report of Bengal and Sikkim, Part-1, Volume-V* in C.K. Paul, *Census Report, 1961*, p.571.
- 18 Debapriya Deb Barman, *Treatise on Traditional Social Institutions of the Tripuri Community*, *op.cit.*, p.57.
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